

Playing with Playford

The English Dancing Master & the English Folk Scene

Jon Boden

John Playford's *The English Dancing Master* (1651) is a point of intersection between early music and the contemporary English folk scene. The melodies it records feature in the early music canon as some of the more modern material regularly performed, and in the English folk scene as the most archaic. For the Early music specialist, Playford marks the end of the process of evolution from Elizabethan courtly dance music towards country dance tunes 'for the masses'; for the folk musician it is a window into the genesis of modern folk music. The material is equally at home in either camp, but the musical interpretations are conditioned by the conventions and instincts of each genre's stylistic mien.

I am a folk musician and have been playing and arranging Playford tunes alongside more modern instrumental folk music for twenty-five years. In this article I will consider the ways in which Playford's English Dancing Master repertoire is used within the English Folk Scene. The guiding assumption in writing this is that all approaches (from period-accurate to synth-pop) are valid and interesting treatments of an important body of melody preserved for us by the efforts of John Playford. It is beyond the scope of this article (and beyond the knowledge and skill-set of the author) to go into any detail about the various musical approaches to Playford within the early music movement. The aim here instead is to present an overview of the ways in which the folk scene utilises Playford's oeuvre within the broader body of folk repertoire, in the hope that it will be of interest to readers coming at it from the early music end of things.

Individual playing style is a huge part of the artistic bedrock of the folk scene that runs in parallel to the regional stylistic tropes of the various traditions.

There is a slight tension between these two stylistic lodestars. On the one hand originality and inimitability are highly prized and the sense that one player is copying another too slavishly is very much looked down upon. On the other hand, the concept of a definable regional style is also highly valued. Either way it is a feature of the English folk scene in particular that players are often striving to define their 'own sound,' whether within an existing stylistic tradition or outside it, and it is this dynamic that informs their stylistic approach to Playford, rather than any historical considerations. Regional and individual style is based upon a number of characteristics that will be employed in varying degrees by each player.

Swing is a musical term normally associated with jazz, but it is a huge feature in traditional music, particularly with bowed and free reed instruments. Different regional styles and different individual players will use swing to varying degrees, but it is always significantly less pronounced, less definite, and less constant than jazz swing. Amongst English-style folk players, swing is sometimes referred to as 'swagger' and this is perhaps a more useful way of thinking about it. It is a musical impulse that toys with the rhythmical assumptions of particular metres – a $\wedge 8$ jig leans into $\$4$, a straight $\$4$ leans into a dotted $\$4$, a waltz leans towards two beats in the bar. It uses listeners' expectations of where the beat(s) should be landing and plays with those assumptions, delaying some notes, hastening others, and in so doing creates tension and release, rhythmic dissonance followed by resolution.

The king-of-swing in English folk fiddle is a man who actually saw himself as a Scottish fiddler, but whose highly individual, anarchic style was mostly employed in English bands and as accompaniment to English singers, generating a huge impact on the development of English fiddle style. Dave

Swarbrick (1941-2016) recorded several Playford melodies and his stately rendition of Dr Isaacs Maggot on his album *Flittin* gives many examples of folk swagger in a seventeenth-century tune.

The use of **implied syncopation** is a close companion of swing/swagger. In jig time (\wedge) most contemporary folk performers will tend to emphasise beats 3 and 6, whereas most early music performers tend to emphasise beats 1 and 4. In $\$4$ tunes most contemporary folk performers will tend to emphasise beats 2 and 4, or at least do more so than their early music counterparts.

A subtle and effective demonstration of this technique is Leveret's 2019 recording of 'Cuckolds All Awry'. Andy Cutting (melodeon) executes much of the implied syncopation, as can be seen from the transcription in example 1.

However, Cutting's actual performance is far more subtle than it is possible to represent in transcription as it is constantly varying in emphasis. In addition, the fiddle (Sam Sweeney) and English concertina (Rob Harbron) tend not to *emphasise* these syncopated beats per se, but instead to play off the melodeon 'groove.' The combination of the (subtly) syncopated melodeon with the not-quite syncopated fiddle and concertina is beguiling and exciting, without allowing the syncopation to overpower the tune.

Of course, there is plenty of syncopation in the Playford tunes themselves, for example in the penultimate bar of 'Cuckolds All Awry', see example 2, but this melodic syncopation is a slightly different type to the implied, emphasis-based syncopation of the folk player. Paradoxically the melodic syncopation of the Playford melodies is very unusual in more modern folk repertoire, at least up until the late twentieth century when tunes such as Catharsis by Amy Cann became very popular and influential.

Padding notes are another element of English folk approaches to Playford's music, exemplified by Leveret (see example 3). Rather than playing the tune as written, Habron, Cutting, and Sweeney instead tend to break long notes down into quavers and pad out the melody with pedal notes or improvised linking passages, getting progressively more elaborate as the tune repeats (transposed to G for reference to the above).

Padding notes and implied syncopation are complementary techniques allowing the folk player to diverge from the written Playford melody without ever fully contradicting it. In extreme cases syncopation and adding notes can turn a tune into something more akin to twentieth-century composed syncopated folk tune, as in Bellowhead's version of 'Childgrove' – the original version and the Bellowhead version can be compared in examples 4 & 5.

Example 1 - Transcription of implied syncopation in 'Cuckolds all awry' as performed by Leveret (2019).

Example 2 - 'Cuckolds all a Row', printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 67 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 3 - 'Cuckolds all awry' with padding notes, as played by Leveret (2019)

Ornamentation is one of the key determiners of regional style within the modern folk scene, particularly amongst fiddle-players. The use of a fingered roll to imitate a triplet, for example, is particularly characteristic of Irish styles, whereas the use of bowed triplets is more associated with Scottish fiddle styles. In most cases these regional styles are fluid, and the modern player will be rooted in one regional style but will use a range of ornaments and other stylistic tropes in the service of defining their own individual style.

English fiddle is slightly different because, unlike Irish and Scottish regional styles, it was left more or less fallow throughout the first half of the twentieth century and so failed to solidify stylistically. To the extent that ornamented English fiddle style can be said to exist at all, it is a modern

invention. Dave Swarbrick has already been mentioned as key in this process. Other fiddlers of his generation (Barry Dransfield, Peter Knight) who played on the English scene also contributed but (like Swarbrick) didn't view themselves as specifically English fiddlers. It was not until the 1990s that the stylistic evolution of English fiddle-playing was solidified. The first of a new generation was Chris Wood, who came to English fiddle via Quebecois and Swedish music and fully embraced it in the band *The English Acoustic Collective* whose 2004 album *Ghosts* included the Playford tunes 'Hare's Maggot' and 'Mr Isaac's Maggot', with two fiddles (Wood & John Dipper) plus Rob Harbron on English concertina. All three players were clearly influenced by Swedish traditional ornamentation as can be seen in their approach to ornamenting 'Mr Isaac's Maggot' (example 6).

Example 4 - 'Childgrove' as found in Henry Playford, *The Dancing-Master* (12th edn; J. Heptinstall, 1703), 261 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 5 - 'Childgrove' as realised by Bellowhead

Example 6 - Transcription of 'Mr. Isaac's Maggot' from *The English Acoustic Collective* recording, Ghost (2004).

Much of folk ornamentation uses the same grace notes as classical ornaments but is very distinct in execution. Most notably, classical players tend to anticipate the beat with their ornaments whereas folk players try to ornament *on* the beat. This also

means that folk ornaments are often executed quicker than their classical counterparts so as to maintain a steady, danceable pulse.

The ‘yup’ – It is a feature of folk music that the technical quirks of the dominant instrument in any particular tradition will often hold stylistic sway over the instruments. For example, the need to use fingered ornaments to distinguish between repeated notes when playing the Highland bagpipes leads naturally to the ‘cran’ ornament (where a low note is rhythmically separated by a series of higher grace notes). It is, however, an entirely unnatural way to separate notes on a fiddle, but the dominance of the pipes within that tradition has led to the development of an imitative fingered fiddle ornament style. Similarly, the characteristic use of rolls as a rhythmical device in Irish piping ornamentation has been adopted by fiddles, flutes, whistles, and accordions in Ireland despite those instruments having far more natural rhythmic mechanisms at their disposal.

In English folk music the dominant instruments, since their invention in the nineteenth century, has been the concertina and melodeon. One of the unusual quirks of these small, light free reed instruments is they naturally lend themselves to the ‘yup,’ that is to say a quick crescendo on a note (creating by a swell in bellows pressure) terminating in a sudden staccato stop (with the release of the fingers.) This yup will often anticipate the beat in its swell, but land solidly on the beat with the stop. This is an extremely useful stylistic feature when trying to make music feel ‘danceable,’ and is particularly utilised when accompanying Cotswold Morris dance, in which the athletic jumping figures are often mimicked musically by this ‘yup’ technique. As it anticipates the beat this also ties into the swing/swagger stylistic elements discussed above.

Using the ‘yup’ is another way in which the folk player will bring these archaic melodies into the

stylistic milieu of contemporary folk, for example when playing ‘Argiers’, John Spiers will often play something akin to the transcription in example 7 for the B music.

Aggression is another variable in folk music that is prized in different measure depending on the regional style. English folk styles tend to fall into the pro-aggression category, as best typified by Eliza Carthy who tackled the Playford tune ‘Stingo’ on her ground-breaking, Mercury-nominated 1998 album *Red Rice* and, later on, with the brass-infused Wayward Band. The fiddle is particularly well suited to an expression of aggression as extreme bow pressure leads to a grungy effect not unlike electric guitar distortion. This is particularly effective when combined with heavy tension double-stopping of open strings.

Tonality, or lack thereof, is one of the interesting features of Playford’s manuscripts, as there is a lack of harmonic information. The tunes are presented monophonically without any indication of where the tonal centre should lie (which would otherwise be made clear through the inclusion of a continuo line). In many tunes the tonality is implicit, but in others it is at the discretion of the player (or the arranger) to make those choices.

A good example of this is the tune ‘Kettledrum’ (example 8). This 1651 edition score is written in what modern readers would interpret as octave bass clef (G1). The band ‘1651’—Andy Cutting (Melodeon), Mark Emmerson (Fiddle, Piano) Tim Harries (Double Bass)—chose to interpret this tune as a driving minor-key melody (example 9 here transposed to D minor) starting on the 2nd note of the scale.

The image shows a musical score for a melody in 4/4 time, written on a single staff. The key signature has one sharp (F#). The melody consists of several measures, each containing a 'yup' ornament. The ornaments are indicated by downward-pointing arrows above the notes. The dynamic markings are *mf*, *p < f*, *mf*, *p < f*, *mf*, *p < f*, *mf*, *p < f*, *mf*. The notation includes slurs, accents, and a final double bar line.

Example 7 - The ‘yup’, as might be played by John Spiers in ‘Argiers’

Kettle Drum

A round Dance for eight

Example 8 – 'Kettledrum', printed in J. Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 89 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 9 - 'Kettledrum' as realised by 1651, harmonised into D minor, written in treble clef (G2).

There is something fundamentally awkward about this harmonic approach - starting on the 2nd note of the scale is discombobulating and concluding the B section with two bars of the tonic chord is, well, weird. The single G# effectively becomes a 'blue' note when used above a Dm harmonisation - not at all in keeping with standard folk sensibilities let alone its seventeenth-century origins. And yet this approach is by far the most common in folk pub sessions. I have written Am in bar one, but in fact it often feels more like a second inversion Dm chord in the '1651's version, again adding to a sense of tension and dissonance by, in effect, beginning the tune with a Dmsus2 chord over an A bass. This awkwardness is actually very appealing to the folkly mindset – in its weirdness, in the potential for dissonance, folkies find excitement and musical drama.

A rarer, and yet more harmonically conventional approach is that of Oxfordshire folk band, Magpie

Lane, who interpret the same melody as being in the major scale (example 10).

This now becomes a gentle, plaintive melody harmonised very simply and consonantly with the tonic, subdominant and dominant alone. There is something inherently contemporary, almost 'pop' about this harmonisation, something beguilingly modern in having both sections end on the dominant chord.

In order to make it work more naturally Magpie Lane have done away with the troublesome G# at the end of bar seven. To the folk mind this sort of alteration is simply part of the evolution of the tune and is entirely in keeping with how the tune *might* have evolved had it survived in the repertoire of, say, a village morris side, accidentals being more or less obliterated by the invention and subsequent preponderance of the diatonic melodeon in the nineteenth century.

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A musical score for 'Kettledrum' in 4/4 time, consisting of three staves. The melody is written on the top staff, and the implied harmony is on the bottom two staves. Chords are indicated above the notes: C, F, C, F, G, C, F, G.

Example 10 - 'Kettledrum' as realised by Magpie Lane.

A historical musical score for 'Kettle Drum' from 'Round for eight'. It features two staves with a complex, rhythmic melody. The notation includes various note values and rests, typical of early printed music.

Example 11 - 'Kettledrum' as printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (2nd edn; London: 1652), 53 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

A musical score for 'Kettledrum' in 4/4 time, consisting of three staves. The melody is written on the top staff, and the implied harmony is on the bottom two staves. Chords are indicated above the notes: A, D, A, D, A, Em, D, E7, A, D, Bm, A, D, A, D.

Example 12 - 'Kettledrum' as presented in Barlow Faber edition, with implied harmony realised by Jon Boden

Another fascinating aspect of all this is that in the second edition of *Dancing Master* (1652), the tonality of the tune is represented entirely differently with the addition of a key signature indicating a tone jump between the first and second notes rather than a semitone (example 11).

This is how it is presented in the Jeremy Barlow Faber edition, and in various online transcriptions. I've never heard this played this way by folkies in 'the wild' - one can only assume the implied harmony would be something along the lines of what is shown in example 12.

This version of the tune has far less appeal to the folk player. The harmonic shifts are too predictable and the whole thing far too staid and polite.

A similar issue is present in 'The Night Piece', first appearing as a strange, haunting D dorian melody (example 13). The same dorian version of the tune is used by the band '1651'. However, in later editions, the addition of a key signature transforms it to a tonally conventional D major (example 14). A great tune but not nearly as intriguing as the dorian version, and of considerably less appeal to the contemporary folk player.

Example 13 - 'The Night Piece' as printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 3 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 14 - 'The Night Piece' as printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (2nd edn; London: 1652), 69 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

If, as seems possible, Playford was correcting transcription mistakes made in the first edition, it leads to the intriguing possibility that some tunes have prospered as session-friendly folk tunes *because* Playford mistakenly omitted key signatures in the original edition. Whether or not that is the case, it is still clear that the harmonic ambiguity of the Playford melodies—both through the lack of notated harmony and through their melodic simplicity—is of great appeal to the folk mindset, allowing different players to come up with radically different versions of ostensibly the same melody.

Harmony — Even where the tonal centre of the melodies is fixed and not in dispute, the whole feel of any given tune is open to huge variations through harmonisation. Whereas the trained early musician will be drawn to harmonisations that reflect practises as determined by treatises, folk players are more likely to actively avoid 'conventional' chord changes and to seek out more modern sounding cadences.

Nineteenth century 'free-reed' instruments such as piano accordion, diatonic melodeon and the various types of concertina are central to the English folk sound, and have a huge impact upon the harmonic conventions of the scene. An extremely common harmonic trope since the 1990s is to hold a low tonic note as a bass drone and play the tonic, sub-dominant and dominant triads above to form a warm but slightly suspended accompaniment. This is particularly favoured by

piano-accordion players as the left hand 'stradella' system makes this the simplest and yet most pleasing (to modern folk ears at any rate) method of harmonising a diatonic major tune.

The duo Belshazzars Feast consisted of fiddle and oboe player extraordinaire Paul Sartin (who sadly passed away in 2022, aged 51) and piano accordion maestro Paul Hutchinson. Paul Hutchinson uses this I/IV/V over a tonic drone figure extensively (alongside far more complex left hand accordion work) and their 2001 album of Playford Tunes *John Playford's Secret Ball* is no exception, such as 'The Garland' ('The Garter' in Playford), example 15. Leveret also uses this extensively on Andy Cutting's melodeon and/or Rob Harbron's concertina, for example in 'Mr Lane's Minuet'.

This approach of diatonic chord-changes played over a drone is also common in guitar accompaniment. Kevin Lees and Sebastian Bloch are a folk duo based in Newcastle Upon Tyne. In an excellent A major arrangement of Grimstock recently posted on their website, Bloch (guitar) takes this approach using open guitar tuning, and the suspension-rich harmony is emphasised by Lees also tuning his fiddle to open A (AEAE) and so is able to add tonic chord harmonisation on double-stopped fiddle when guitar is playing any of the six diatonic major/minor chords underneath.

Improvisation and variation are a huge part of English tune playing, even more so than in the

more established Scottish/Irish/Swedish folk playing traditions. In the pub session context improvisation is normally in the form of short phrases that either harmonise with, counterpoint to, or create dynamic tension with the primary melody being played collectively. The spaciousness of Playford tunes lend themselves well to this approach, particularly inviting contrapuntal extemporisation, as illustrated by the Leveret and English Acoustic Collective examples above.

More free-form improvisation (akin to jazz soloing) is very rare in folk tune playing contexts, but not unheard of. It's interesting that two of the few bands from the folk scene who are specifically interested in using more free-form improvisation, were/are also specifically focused on the Playford repertoire: 'The Playford Liberation Front' and '1651'.

The Playford Liberation Front (who continue to perform) utilise a reasonably conventional folk-band line up (accordion, fiddle, bass guitar, pipes) but unusually add a soloistic, improvisatory clarinet line over the top, reminiscent of Klezmer.

Even more unusually the band 1651 built whole pieces around the stating of a Playford melody, followed by an extended improvised section played over a drone or over the chord-changes established during the opening section.

Group arrangement approaches

The approach to ensemble arrangement within the folk scene is different to early music methods. There is a tendency in the folk scene to try to use modern instruments, or at least modern versions of old instruments. So, for example, ninety percent of guitars employed in the folk scene are steel-strung acoustics rather than gut/nylon strung. With Victorian instruments such as melodeons and accordions, these now tend to be 'dry tuned' to sound more contemporary than heavy 'beating' of Jimmy Shand-style tunings that were popular in the first half of the twentieth century. Oboes and clarinets are not exactly common in the English folk scene, but they are far more common than

period wind instruments (shawms, crumhorns etc.) Period string instruments such as viols and lutes are hardly ever used and even recorders are generally eschewed in favour of the Victorian-era tin whistle. One area of instrumental crossover is with bagpipes and hurdy gurdies. Unlike in Ireland, the English bagpipe did not evolve into a sophisticated eighteenth century instrument, so when bagpipes are used they tend to be fairly similar in timbre to period instruments (John Swayne's 'English Border Pipes' being the most common on the English folk scene) and hurdy gurdies are (as far as I'm aware) built and set up the same whether played for early or folk music (though the stylistic approach, particularly in the syncopated use of the rhythmical 'trompette' is quite distinct.) Hurdy gurdies and bagpipes are more associated with the strong French/Euro Folk music scene (often socially linked to, but distinct from, the English Folk scene), the band 'Blowzabella' (named after the Playford tune) being the key exponents in England.

Conventional drum kits are fairly common in the English scene (on the concert performance end of things rather than the session scene) and have often been used with Playford tunes. The classic folk-rock sound typified by drummer Dave Mattacks maps on to Playford's 'Picking of Sticks' without difficulty (example 16).

An interest in the use of brass instruments has been a small but significant element of the English folk scene since the 1970s, most notably in that decade in the form of Brass Monkey, who fused a marching brass-band feel with melodeon-led English repertoire. Example 17 includes the *Dancing Master* tune 'Dr Fauster's Tumblers'.

Other English folk bands have experimented with pop-style brass sections, perhaps most recognisably with my own band Bellowhead, who have tackled several Playford tunes including 'Childgrove' (mentioned above), 'Argiers' and 'Parson's Farewell' (see example 18).

The image shows a musical score for 'The Garland'. The top system is for an accordion, with a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. The melody is written in the treble staff, and the bass staff contains chords. The bottom system is for a piano, with a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. The melody is written in the treble staff, and the bass staff contains chords. There are repeat signs and first/second endings in both systems. A bracket under the piano bass staff indicates a specific rhythmic pattern.

Example 15 - 'The Garland', as played by Belshazzar's Feast. *John Playford's Secret Ball*. 2018.

The image shows a musical score for 'Picking of Sticks'. It features four staves: Descant Recorder, Drum Set, Electric Guitar, and Bass Guitar. The time signature is 8/8. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 120. The Descant Recorder staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The Drum Set staff has a double bar line and a key signature of one sharp. The Electric Guitar staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The Bass Guitar staff has a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. There are repeat signs and first/second endings in the Descant Recorder and Electric Guitar staves.

Example 16 - 'Picking of Sticks' with added Drum Kit

This 'festival band brass' approach was also employed to great effect by Eliza Carthy and The Wayward Band in their version of the Playford tune *Stingo*. Playford melodies in their original form tend to have simple, clean melodic lines compared to more modern folk tunes. This melodic clarity lends itself to contrapuntal brass stabs as a) there is space for them and b) the melodies themselves are more likely to suggest suitable brass lines that echo the main melody.

As has been mentioned, the folk scene tends to be drawn to modern instrumentation and eschew period instruments. It is not wholly surprising therefore that many folk performers over the years have been drawn to digital music making, or EDM (Electronic Dance Music.) Notable exponents of this in the Scottish and Irish scenes include Martyn

Bennet and The Afro Celt Sound System. In general, English folk tunes have not proved quite as amenable to digital arrangement (probably because of the need to maintain swing - see above) but several performers have experimented with it, for example Eliza Carthy with her 1998 track *Red Rice*.

Again, the melodic simplicity of Playford tunes lends itself more to a digital approach than heavily swung Morris tunes or complex country dance tunes, but it is still quite surprising to discover that no less than three artists (James Bell, Ben & Sel, and Chris Green) have experimented with fully digital arrangements of Playford tunes. In this extreme, digital-only format there is so little of the stylistic features of the folk scene (as detailed above) remaining that objectively they have no

more, or less, to do with the folk scene than they do with early music practices. But the fact that these artists all come from/interface with the folk scene rather than the early music scene is illustrative of their being part of a continuum of experimental folk-scene approaches to Playford, albeit on the extreme wing.

Folk sessions - conventions and transpositions

Any musician, from whatever musical background, turning up to a pub folk session in England who has memorised some Playford tunes is likely to find that many of the other players in the room will know them and happily join in. However, it's worth noting that folk sessions (whilst in many ways inclusive and welcoming) do have a whole series of unspoken rules that it is easy for the newcomer to miss or be flummoxed by. One such rule is that sheet music is never used - if you haven't memorised it, don't play it. Tunes tend to be played in sets of three, often with each tune being played three times round. A feature of folk sessions that is second nature to regular attendees is that tunes tend to only be played in certain keys. There is some leeway with this but in general keys that can readily be played on a D major tin whistle are favoured: D & G major (A at a push), E and A minor(s), B aeolian, D dorian at a push. Therefore, it is very likely that any Playford tunes that are played will not be played in the key in which they have been published. A musical newcomer to folk sessions turning up with a repertoire of Playford tunes might therefore be well advised to learn them in one of these keys in preference to the written key.

Conclusions – There are a huge number of recorded versions of Playford melodies within the English folk scene and the repertoire continues to maintain a strong presence in English folk pub sessions. Why do so many folk musicians choose to play Playford? There are many eighteenth- and nineteenth-century manuscripts that contain tunes that are more of a piece with contemporary folk tune repertoire: folk tune players may dip into this or that collection to find tunes, but no single manuscript comes even close to Playford in terms

of ubiquity within the folk scene. The Playford repertoire is at the same time outlier and core repertoire.

As mentioned above, a paradox of the unspoken philosophy of the English Folk Scene is that it performs antiquated material whilst being highly preoccupied with its contemporary relevance. Music, for the folk musician, is about evolution not antiquity, about furthering 'the tradition' rather than recreating the past. The 'composed' (whether from the seventeenth or the twenty-first century) is often seen as of less weight than material which has been passed down through a number of generations. The guiding philosophy behind these underpinning value judgements is in part Darwinian, but more importantly it is collectivist - the sense that material with no single author is in some way owned by everyone. This has even led to a culture of sublimated authorship – of folk musicians downplaying their own creative input (or in extreme cases completely inventing a fake traditional source) in order for their composed or semi-composed material to be accepted as legitimately 'traditional' by the folk scene at large.

Playford's place within this is complex. On the one hand there is something a little too 'composed' about many of the tunes for conventional folk taste, and some of the more baroque cadences are tolerated rather than enjoyed by the folk player. And yet the Playford repertoire has so much to offer the folk player that is often not present in more modern repertoire. The melodic simplicity affords the player huge scope in terms of individual interpretation and musical reinvention. The lack of a defined stylistic framework means each player can bring to bear their own musical proclivities. Playford melodies are, comparatively speaking, a blank canvas upon which the folk-player can paint their own stylistic, harmonic, ornamental, genre-bending conceptions of contemporary folk 'Englishness' and, despite (or, perhaps, *because of*) being further removed chronologically than any other material played, it is often in the Playford repertoire that English folk players find the apotheosis of their own personal style. There is a

sense in which, to the folk musician's mind, the Playford tunes represent pre-evolved folk tunes, so the modern player feels empowered to mimic the evolutionary process of three hundred and fifty years of aural transmission through their own musical mediation.

In short folk players keep coming back to Playford because these seventeenth-century tunes are useful in the folk player's mission to sound individual, contemporary, edgy, and experimental whilst staying rooted within established traditions and grounded in a sense of historical legitimacy. And, of course, because they are great tunes to play.

Jon Boden

A musical score for two instruments: Trumpet / concertina and Trombone. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 2/4. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 78. The Trumpet part features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, while the Trombone part provides a harmonic accompaniment with chords and moving lines.

Example 17 – ‘Doctor Fauster’s Tumblers’ as played by Brass Monkey. ‘Doctor Fauster’s Tumblers/The Night of Trafalgar/Prince William’. *The Complete Brass Monkey*. 1983.

A musical score for a full brass band. The score includes parts for Melody, Soprano Saxophone, Trumpet in Bb, Trombone, Sousaphone in Bb, and Drum Set. The key signature is one flat (Bb) and the time signature is 2/4. The score is divided into two systems, with the second system starting at measure 9. The Melody part is the primary melodic line, while the other instruments provide harmonic support and rhythmic accompaniment.

Example 18 - 'Parson's Farewell' as played by Bellowhead. Reassembled. 2021.

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Select Discography

Band/Artist(s)	Track	Album (and Link)	Date
Albion Dance Band	Picking of Sticks / The Old Mole	The Prospect Before Us	1977
Bellowhead	Parson's farewell	Reassembled	2021
Belshazzar's Feast	All tracks Playford	John Playford's Secret Ball	2018
Ben and Sel	The Shepherd and Shepherdess	Traditional Tunes in a New Style	2023
Blackbeards Tea Party	Hummeabar (Kettledrum)	Heaven's to Betsy	2009
Brass Monkey	Doctor Fauster's Tumblers / The Night of Trafalgar / Prince William	The Complete Brass Monkey	1983
Chris Green	All tracks Playford	Switched on Playford	2018
Eliza Carthy	Stingo	Red Rice	1998
English Acoustic Collective	Hare's Maggot / Mr Isaac's Maggot	Ghosts	2004
James Bell	The Shepherd and Shepherdess	Unreleased track	2011
John Kirkpatrick	Once I Loved a Maiden Fair / The Hole in the Wall / Amaryllis	One Man and His Box	1999
Jumpleads	Hunt The Squirrel, La Montarde	The Stag Must Die	1982
Kevin Lees & Sebastian Bloch	Grimstock	The Good Tune	2024
Leveret	Mr Lane's Minuet	Forms	2023
Playford Liberation Front	Trip To Kilburn (Black and Grey)	Three Track Demo	2016
Spiers & Boden	Jack Robinson / Argiers / Old Tom of Oxford	Bellow	2004